

Assessment of Long-Term Structural Changes in a VVER-1000 Reactor Flange Stud

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Abstract. The long-term operation of nuclear power plants depends on the properties of the components' structural materials and their resistance to radiation, corrosion, and thermo-mechanical strains for longer than 60-80 years. The integrity of primary circuit components is essential to ensure high nuclear safety. This paper studies microstructural changes in a reactor flange fastening system, especially in a flange stud and nut exposed to irradiation and a gradually varying thermo-mechanical load. The investigated flange stud and nut originate from a Ukrainian VVER 1000 reactor and were analysed through the DELISA-LTO project with the aim to evaluate the long-term resistance of the primary circuit components in VVER technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The reactor flange fastening system (Fig. 1a) is a critical component of nuclear power plants (NPP) used to securely and tightly close the reactor pressure vessel (RPV) during operation. The studs and nuts are subjected to cyclic exposure to high temperatures, mechanical stress, and radiation from neutrons and gamma rays. They are produced from highly mechanically resistant low-alloyed steels; for VVER 1000, the material is 38KhN3MFA, which has high toughness and low creep. As the studs and nuts are directly in contact with RPV and are cooled by air over RPV, the thermal conduction causes the gradient of thermal strain, as is shown in Fig. 1b.

FIGURE 1. Reactor fastening system: Scheme of stud and nut (a); Temperature gradient in the fastening system during nominal NPP operation (b); investigated samples (c).

During the project, DELISA-LTO, one reactor stud and one nut were gained for research after an operation of 30 years in NPP with the VVER1000 reactor (Fig. 1c). Although the DELISA-LTO project mainly focuses on comparing the structure of materials before and after the NPP operation, unfortunately, the stud and nut materials did not have an initial state. Thus, we can compare only these two materials based on two different temperatures during NPP operation. The material of the stud and nut was cut into smaller parts and delivered for measurements. The material ageing and microstructural changes after 30 years of operation in NPP were monitored in the samples, and the first prediction about the long-term changes of the component and its resistance was made. Over the decades of NPP operation, their microstructure was changing, and processes such as tempering of martensite, carbide coarsening, and precipitation ageing were predicted there. These can increase residual stresses and concentration of microstructural defects, followed by material integrity weakness and microcrack formation.

EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES AND METHODS

The samples from the stud and nut were experimentally studied for microstructural change after **30 years** of operation in VVER 1000. The chemical composition of the stud and nut construction material - 38KhN3MFA is shown in Tab.1, and mechanical properties in Tab.2. The first sample (**sample D**) was prepared for the nut located in the upper part of the fastening system during the NPP operation with a temperature of **240°C**. The second sample (**sample C**) was from the bottom part of the stud grounded in the RPV with an operation temperature of **305°C**. The samples were cut from the delivered material into small dimensions of 1 cm x 1 cm x 0.2 cm, ground with grit size from 200 to 1800, and finally polished at a vibration polishing system with diamond paste D9 and D3.

TABLE 1. Chemical composition of investigated stud from VVER 1000 reactor material 38KhN3MFA (wt. %).

C	Si	Mn	Cr	Ni	Mo	V	S	P	Cu
0.33	0.17	0.25	1.20	3.00	0.35	0.10	0.025	0.025	0.30
÷	÷	÷	÷	÷	÷	÷			
0.40	0.37	0.50	1.50	3.50	0.45	0.18			

TABLE 2. Mechanical properties of material 38KhN3MFA according to the GOST standard 23304-78 at two different temperatures: Rm is tensile strength, Rp0.2 is yield strength and KCV is fracture toughness.

T (°C)	Rm (MPa)	Rp0.2 (MPa)	KCV (J/sm ²)
20	981	880	59
350	834	746	-

The influence of temperature variation and positional differences relative to the RPV was investigated using two complementary non-destructive techniques. Defect characterisation was performed by positron annihilation spectroscopy (PAS), employing positron lifetime and coincidence Doppler broadening methods to probe open-volume defects. Residual stresses were assessed through Barkhausen noise analysis, offering insights into stress distribution across the studied regions. Additionally, the microstructural features of the material were examined using optical microscopy to support and correlate the findings. All techniques were applied at non-destructive testing laboratories at the Slovak University of Technology.

Positron annihilation lifetime spectroscopy (PALS) can monitor small open-volume defects such as mono-, di-vacancies and dislocations. The PALS results are presented in positron lifetimes proportional to the size of defects and intensities describing defect concentration. The Coincidence Doppler Broadening Spectroscopy (CDBS) observes positron annihilation energy and its change due to the spin of the annihilation electron. This technique is sensitive to the chemical surroundings of the annihilation place. The results are given in S and W parameters, where the S parameter describes annihilation in defects and the W parameter annihilation with electrons of surrounding atoms. Both positron annihilation techniques, PALS and CDBS, were measured with a Combined Triple Coincidence Positron Lifetime and Coincidence Doppler Broadening Measurement Setup [1].

The Barkhausen Noise Measurement (BNM) is sensitive to residual stress changing with external loads such as thermo-mechanical strain or irradiation. The microstructure can change under stress by creating defects, precipitations, or changes in iron phases. Microstructural changes can affect magnetic domain movement in the external magnetic field during BNM measurement, resulting in a decreased magnetic response, i.e. lower Root-Mean-Square value (RMS) and Peak parameters (BNM peak) or changing of peak position (Hpeak position). RMS and Hpeak are

parameters proportional to the inverse value of residual stress or magnetic domain movement [2]. For BNM measurements, the Stresstech Rollscan 350 was applied with the Microscan 500 program [3].

Finally, optical microscopy (OM) was used to obtain an image of the sample C structure to find changes due to operation at 305°C temperatures for 30 years. Sample C was observed after etching at Nital for 10 seconds.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Positron annihilation lifetime measurement

Samples C and D were analysed using PALS, and the resulting data were fitted using the LT9 program [4]. Figure 2a presents the obtained positron lifetime components. The first lifetime (LT1), approximately 140 ps, corresponds to positron annihilation at defect-free structure and dislocations. The second component (LT2) reflects longer lifetimes, indicative of open-volume defects. Specifically, LT2 corresponds to di-vacancy-type defects in Sample C, while Sample D is associated with larger clusters, such as four- or five-vacancy complexes. These results confirm that Sample D contains larger defects than Sample C.

FIGURE 2. Positron annihilation lifetime results: Positron lifetimes (LT) proportional to defect size (a); Positron intensity (I) proportional to defect concentration (b).

Figure 2b presents the intensities corresponding to individual positron lifetimes, reflecting the fraction of positrons annihilated within each specific lifetime component. These intensities are proportional to the concentration of all defects, with sensitivity typically spanning from approximately 10^{10} to 10^{17} cm^{-3} . Sample C, associated with di-vacancy defects, exhibits a higher intensity of 24.2%, whereas Sample D, containing larger open-volume defects, shows a lower intensity of 8.4%. This reduced intensity in Sample D indicates a lower defect concentration; however, the larger defect size results in a greater overall defect volume. This observation is supported by the Mean Positron Lifetime value (MLT): Sample C shows an MLT of 152 ps, while Sample D reaches 158 ps. This difference of 6 ps between the two samples confirms the presence of larger defect volumes in Sample D compared to Sample C. According to the general theory [5] and our practice, the MLT values for non-stressed material can be between 120 and 140 ps after manufacturing. The MLT of the samples C and D are much higher, which indicates significant structure degradation during the NPP operation.

Coincidence Doppler Broadening measurements

The CDBS technique was used to observe the presence of open-volume defects by the S parameter and the chemical surroundings of the annihilation place by the W parameter. Samples C and D have almost the same S parameter with values 1.04 (C) and 1.041 (D), which generally indicates the presence of minor open-volume defects

- dislocations, which are in major presence as PALS identified them with more than 70% intensities. The CDBS results are shown in Fig. 3.

The W parameter was compared with pure metals such as iron, chromium, manganese, and nickel. However, these elements probably do not significantly affect positron annihilation in our samples, as no curve is identical to the samples. Thus, the annihilation surroundings are a mixture of these elements or may contain other elements present in chemical contents (as C, Mo, V).

FIGURE 3. The ratio of the CDBS annihilation spectra for the investigated samples C and D to the reference iron spectrum. Comparison of samples C and D with other reference materials (Mn, Ni, and Cr) from the samples' content.

Barkhausen noise measurements

BNM was supplemented by sample A – the upper part of the stud (near nut) operating at 240°C for 30 years. The comparison between samples A and D can show a difference due to mechanical strain, and the comparison between samples A and C can indicate the effect of temperature. The positron measurements for this sample were not performed due to problems with sample preparation for these techniques. BNM measurement was applied 5 times for all samples; average values were calculated and are presented (Fig. 4).

The BNM results show that the lowest residual stress level is localised in sample A, which is the upper part of the stud (lower temperature and lower mechanical stress). This sample showed the highest value of BNM peak - 26 mV with an average RMS of 25 mV. Sample C from the bottom part of the stud showed that its BNM values do not differ significantly from sample A; the average RMS was around 18 mV, and the BNM peak was 25 mV. The lowest values appeared for sample D – nut, with an RMS value of 9 mV and a BNM peak value of 10 mV.

FIGURE 4. BNM results are shown in the magnetic burst profile and RMS, BNM, and Hpeak values.

The Hpeak position indicates the presence of a martensitic structure or a huge content of carbides in all samples, as their values exceeded 40% of the magnetisation current. The optical microscopy showed a tempered martensitic structure (Fig. 5), which was also expected after 30 years at a temperature between 200 and 300 °C, where carbides and ferrites should be formed. According to BNM data, the strong influence of formed carbides was found. Carbides work there as domain pinning sites and restrict domain movement, suppressing noise signals and keeping the signal in a higher Hpeak position.

FIGURE 5. The optical micrograph reveals a tempered martensitic structure.

CONCLUSION

All experimental techniques applied to measure the reactor flange nut and stud revealed the presence of microstructural defects, predominantly dislocations, where positron trapping was saturated. The difference between the flange stud and nut lies in their operating temperatures and the different mechanical strains exposed throughout their service life. The nut was primarily subjected to compressive stress, whereas the stud was mainly under tensile stress. Consequently, a significant difference in Barkhausen noise values was observed. The upper part of the stud was exposed to minimal temperature and mechanical stress and, therefore, exhibited the lowest residual stress.

In contrast, the bottom part of the stud operated at a higher temperature of approximately 65°C. The nut is the most mechanically stressed fastening component, with compressive stress contributing to higher residual stress. This condition likely promotes the formation of larger defects, such as four- and five-vacancy clusters, which may serve as nucleation sites for microcracks, leading to potential loss of integrity. Fortunately, flange nuts and studs are replaceable

and should probably be exchanged during the NPP lifetime. The presence of dislocations is typical for tempered martensite and is responsible for the characteristic hardness but maintains highly needed components' dimensional stability.

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REFERENCES

1. M. Petriska, S. Sojak, V. Kršjak, J. Degmová, and V. Slugeň, AIP Conf. Proc. **2778**, 060007 (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0135885>
2. M. Honkanen, S. Santa-aho, L. Laurson, N. Eslahi, A. Foi, and M. Vippola, Acta Mater. **221**, 117378 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2021.117378>
3. J. Degmová, V. Kršjak, S. Sojak, J. Dekan, M. Petriska, P. Mikula, and M. Kotvas, J. Nucl. Mater. **547**, 152799 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2021.152799>
4. J. Kansy, Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. A **374**, 235–244 (1996).
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002\(96\)00075-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002(96)00075-7)
5. P. Hautojärvi, *Positrons in Solids* (Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1979), pp. 258.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-81316-0>